

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B044
Date: 28 Aug 2004
Take Off: 08:16:08
Landing: 13:10:06
Flight Time: 4h53m58

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols near Venice ocean tower

Operating Area: N Adriatic, near Venice, N Italy

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Simon Osborne	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
11	AMS	Keith Bower	UMIST
12	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
13	Mission Scientist 2	Jim Haywood	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
15	Mission Scientist 4	Nicolas Bellouin	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 5	Gunnar Myhre	University of Oslo
17	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
18			
19			

Flight Track:

B044 Track 28-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B044
 Date: 28-AUG-2004
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: Treviso

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
064300		EVM 1	0.00 kft	000	UBBR zero start
065400		EVM 2	0.0 kft	023	UBBR zero end
081608		T/O	0.0 kft	245	From Treviso
082542		Videos	1.7 kft	093	Start recording
082750	083349	Profile 1	50ft - 3.1 kft	172	500fpm
083401	084424	Profile 1	3.4 - 15.0 kft	176	1000fpm Interrupt
084656	085740	Profile 1	15.0 - 25.0 kft	347	1000fpm
090011	090202	Orbit 1	25.0 kft	241	45deg,LH,start 240
090210	090353	Orbit 2	25.1 - 25.0 kft	210	
090948	091147	Orbit 3	23.0 kft	035	45deg,LH,start 030
091147	091353	Orbit 4	23.0 kft	042	
091353	091552	Orbit 5	23.0 kft	041	
091553	091752	Orbit 6	23.0 - 22.9 kft	045	
093907	094118	Orbit 7	23.0 - 22.9 kft	238	40deg,LH,start 240
094118	094328	Orbit 8	22.9 kft	234	
094328	094537	Orbit 9	22.9 kft	235	
094537	094753	Orbit 10	22.9 kft	240	
095216	100217	Run 1.1	25.1 - 25.0 kft	149	Box pattern, Into Sun
100357	100855	Run 1.2	25.0 kft	243	Across Sun
101539	102512	Run 1.3	25.0 - 25.1 kft	338	Down Sun
103127	103639	Run 1.4	25.0 kft	073	Across Sun
103823	104337	Profile 2	24.9 - 19.4 kft	252	1000fpm
104455	104739	Profile 2	19.3 - 15.8 kft	073	Interrupt
104832	105305	Profile 2	15.7 - 10.6 kft	172	
105437	105720	Profile 2	10.5 - 8.0 kft	000	
110001	111001	Run 2	8.0 kft	179	
111204	111508	Profile 3	8.0 - 5.5 kft	358	1000fpm
111519	112512	Run 3	5.4 - 5.5 kft	002	
112721	112841	Profile 4	5.5 - 4.5 kft	191	
112855	113844	Run 4	4.4 - 4.5 kft	189	
113317		Videos	4.5 kft	188	Change tapes
114236	114412	Profile 5	4.5 - 3.5 kft	017	
114413	114928	Run 5	3.5 kft	015	
115219	115544	Profile 6	3.5 - 1.4 kft	201	500fpm , Interrupt
115740	115953	Profile 6	1.3 - 0.02 kft	023	
120350	121251	Run 6	100ft	200	Into Sun
122155		Heimann	0.46 kft	354	Cal
122406	122537	Orbit 11	400ft	272	39deg,LH,start 270
122537	122714	Orbit 12	400ft	273	
122714	122848	Orbit 13	400ft	274	
122848	123017	Orbit 14	400ft	267	
124042	124214	Orbit 15	400ft	272	40deg,LH,start 270
124214	124343	Orbit 16	400ft	278	
124343	124511	Orbit 17	400ft	136	
124512	124639	Orbit 18	400ft	266	
124711	125159	Profile 7	400ft- 4.9 kft	162	1000fpm
125200	125250	Run 7	4.9 kft	152	1000fpm
125803	130304	Run 8	4.9 kft	299	
131006		Land	0.0 kft	023	Treviso

B044 Track 28-AUG-04

11°E

12°E

13°E

14°E

11°E

12°E

13°E

14°E

METMAN FLIGHT

SATURDAY 28/08/04

G-LUXE Ba146

Callsign: Metman1

Max FL150

100 ft

A 3000Ft

FL250

100 ft

Up to FL250

FL50

3000 ft

FL150

FL100

FL250

0498230297

Ufficio Operazioni

27 Ago 04 14:21

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight number: B044

Date 28th August 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols near Venice ocean tower.

Weather: Predominantly cloud free. Advection of light pollution into the area.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off Treviso 08:00Z and maneuver at low level to point A (Ocean Tower: 45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E) (10mins)
2. Interrupted profile ascent from 50ft to FL250, breaking once to bring back to point A. (40mins)
3. Over point A, release dropsonde#1
4. Set of 4 banked orbits at FL250 banked at solar zenith angle (~45°) (50mins)
5. 10 minute holding pattern (60mins)
6. Set of 4 banked orbits at FL250 banked at solar zenith angle (~ 45°) (70mins)
7. Box pattern at FL250 comprising 10 minute into-sun, 5 min across sun, 5 min down sun and 5 min across sun (100 mins)
8. Release Dropsonde#2
9. Broken profile descent to FL150 to overhead point A (110mins)
10. Stacked profile descent with SLRs of 10 minute duration oriented into- and down- sun at five levels (called by the aircraft scientist) between FL150 and 100ft (190mins)
11. Set of 4 banked orbits at 400ft banked at solar zenith angle (~35°) (200mins)
12. 10 minute holding pattern (210mins)
13. Set of 4 banked orbits at 400ft banked at solar zenith angle (~35°) (220mins)
14. Stacked profile ascent comprising SLRs of 10 minute duration oriented into- and down-sun at five levels (called by the aircraft scientist) between 100ft and FL150. (275mins)
15. Release Dropsonde#3
16. Recover to Treviso.

Aircraft Scientist de-brief sheet

Flight number: B044

Date: 28th August 2004

Sortie objectives:

To carry out in-situ and radiometric measurements of industrial pollution advecting over the northern Adriatic Sea from the Po valley, in conjunction with the Venice instrumented ocean tower (designated point A) at 45°18'51" N, 12°30'29" E.

Weather conditions:

With the thundery trough having passed through the area two days previously in a SE'ly direction, conditions allowed pollution to build up in the Po valley and to advect over our operating region. High pressure ridging from the west, with predominantly stable conditions and light winds at low level over the region. Mostly cloud free over the sea areas except for very small cu/small patches of sc hugging coastal regions.

Summary of the flight:

A very successful sortie was carried out that constituted the 2nd ADRIEX flight. Pollution was successfully sampled that had advected over the region out of the Po valley. The initial profile ascent from 50' to FL250 revealed the main pollution layer was between 4500'-6500'. Some more localised pollution events were sampled at ~2500'. Two sets of 4 45° orbits were carried out at FL230 over point A (the initial attempt at FL250 proved too high) above all significant pollution, with the SWS filter change between the two sets. The captain's primary instruments failed during these orbits and so the remaining orbits of the sortie were flown in a cruder manner, yet still with acceptable results. A box pattern was then carried out at FL250, orientated into-, across-, down- and across- Sun. The lower BBR clear flux was about 64 W/m². We ran over the coast during R1.2 and so the end of R1.2 and start of R1.3 will show land effects, even after some re-positioning for the start of R1.3 A profile descent to FL080 was carried out to start the first SLR into-Sun. This run was just above the pollution layer, which was clearly visible to the naked eye. Further afield (perhaps over land), cu were forming on the top of the pollution, presumably seeded by the pollution aerosol. Further 10 min runs were then carried out at 5500', 4500' and 3500' (orientated down, into and down Sun, respectively), all of which were within pollution, although the 3500' leg (R5) showed counts dropping off. CO values were ~130 ppbv within the layer, PAN values were a very high 2 ppb; CN counts were ~7500/cc. Filters were exposed during these runs. A final SLR was carried out at 100'. The aerosol characteristics were different here from the elevated pollution above. CN values were up to 10⁴ /cc, although the aerosol was generally non-uniform here. A strong pollution plume (more localised compared to the general, more aged(?) Po valley pollution aloft) was sampled during this leg, showing a remarkably Gaussian shape. The aerosol mass spec indicated different aerosol chemistry here compared to aloft. After re-positioning at point A, two sets of four 40° orbits were successfully

performed at 400'. There was no cloud hindrance during any of the orbits in this flight. Time only permitted a profile ascent to 5000' to carry out a couple of legs within the pollution. During this ascent, two distinct pollution layers were observed by eye further afield to the port side, with the layers being in close proximity but clearly defined in the vertical.

Aerosol optical depths were greater than during B043. AERONET sites suggested the 0.44 μm AODs were 0.152 (ISDGM, central Venice), 0.119 (ocean tower, point A) and 0.127 (Nicelli airport). The data will show an interesting contrast with B043 in relatively high aerosol loadings.

Instrument status:

Drift on the lower BBRs during SLRs, of about 5-10 W/m^2 . Neph and PSAP behaved much better than B043. CVI PCASP 1st channel out, but probe seems to be measuring very low counts. Wing-mount PCASP without bottom 3 bins; reason for failing amplifiers on the PCASP unknown. FFSSP over-heating ? No sondes were dropped due to permission not begin granted.

S.R. Osborne.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S. P. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.044**.....

Date **28/08/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0816					Take off Treviso Airport.
					Tr. Cu to left, + right. Merizedeas. Elevated haze visible. Clearlet below us. ground?
0824		5000'			Tr. Cu over sea. whitish haze at or below us.
0825					descending to 5000ft to dust profile
082633		4000'	173	45.2 12.5	Passing ocean tower to our right
082751	P17	5000'		45.2 12.5	Start profile ascent.
					cn ~ 6000cc some large spikes.
082917					Tr. Cu ahead. clear generally. CUE PCASP ~ 250/cc.
		2000'			(scattered plant to right?) hit pollution plume ~ 2000
		2700'			Out of plume phase ~ 19000cc
083510		2000' 4600'			1000ft/min. $w_{0.96} \sim 0.96$.
		3000'			Back into pollution. CN ~ 10000cc
					CUE PCASP ~ 70/cc low!!
083700		9000'			Very clear of pollution layer now.
084142		12000'			Totally clear above. Small Cu field to our left.
		FL140			dry slot on TD. left turn.
084427	P17	FL150	166	46.2 12.7	Intercept profile ascent
084630					2 layers of cloud to our left
084650	P17	FL150	347	46.3 12.9	windy w_{258} Re-start profile ascent
085246	P17	FL250	337	45.0 12.6	End profile ascent.

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 Flight No **B.044**.....
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 Date 28/02/04.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
085959		R250			Some light Cu below us.
090010	01 [↓]	R250			45° banked Bunbank orbits, left wing down. Ozser = 45.55° good! clear skies above.
090353	02 [↑]	R250			Some Cu-Sc below, off set from us. Not good 45° for 02. Good orbit, cannot maintain angle descending directly below us.
090947	03 [↑]	R230	030	45.1 12.6	Start set of orbit again. 45° Ozser = 44.47°
091144	04	R230		45.1 12.5	next orbit. Tr. Cu directly below us.
091352	05	R230			next orbit.
091551	06	R230		45.0 12.6	next orbit (1 st set) climb to R250 for holding runs. SWS nearly empty!
093906	07 [↑]	R230		45.2 12.4	Start desc (2 nd set) ~ 40° → pilot's guess INS not working quite a bit.
094120	08 [↑]	R230		45.2 12.4	SWS empty! (36-45°) clear skies down Sc still hugging coast.
094327	09 [↑]	R230		45.2 12.5	
094539	010 [↑]	R230		45.2 12.5	last orbit started. Ozser = 40.12° @ 094652
094752	010	R230		45.2 12.6	End set of orbit.
095217	R1.1	R250	152	44.8 12.8	Climbing to R250 for SWC pattern STC Run into Sun Ozser = 148.7° Lower flux $\approx 61 \text{ W/m}^2$
100218	R1.1	R250	152	44.1 13.5	End STC Run into Sun.

Ozser = 152°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100354	R1.2	FL250	262	44.0 13.4	Start S+L Run across Sun.
100934	R1.2				Over coast!!
100958	R1.2	FL250	245	43.9 12.9	End run across Sun.
					outside turn. Position over sea!!!
101539	R1.3	FL250	339	44.1 12.8	Start S+L run. still see effects of westward ^{lower} SBRs..
					clear below + above.
					Extending run for SBRs.
102525					lower clear than = 64 w/m ²
102515	R1.3	FL250	362	44.0 12.5	End Run
103128	A.4	FL250	073	45.1 12.4	Start run across Sun. moving away from coast.
103639	A.4	FL250	074	45.2 13.1	End S+L Run (box pattern!!)
					lower SBR than dropping off - lower coast?!
103823	P2↓	FL250	254	45.3 13.1	Start profile descent - 1000 ft/min
104338	P2→	FL190	258	45.2 12.5	white haze below us. End of profile descent.
104458	P2↓	FL190	072	45.2 12.5	Re-start profile descent.
104740	P2→	FL158	078	45.2 12.9	Intermittent profile descent.
104833	P2↓	FL158	071	45.2 12.9	Re-start profile descent.
105306	P2→	FL105	?	44.9 12.9	Intermittent profile
105437	P2↓	FL105	358	44.7 12.9	Re-start profile descent.
					No sig. aerosol here
					Tr. Cu below. ^{As} totally clear above.
105722	P2.	FL070	003	45.1 11.9	End profile descent
					prepare for 1 st run - into

Ca bubbling on top of Sun.
pollution over land ahead.
nothing here cause!!

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...064...**

 Date **28/08/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110003		FL080	079	45.1 12.8	
111003	P2	FL080	178	44.4 12.8	End Run.
111201	P3		358	44.5 12.8	Start profile descent to next level
111519	P3	5000'	004		End profile descent
111520	P3	5000'	004	44.7 12.8	Start Run in pollution - good hits on neph. Trace gas analysis AMS also. CO ~ 130 ppbv (?)
112500	P3	5500'	005	45.3 12.9	End Run in top of pollution layer.
112721	P4 ↓	5500'	191	45.3 12.8	Start profile descent <u>Descent = 187'</u>
112839	P4 →	4500'	189	(45.2 12.8)	End profile descent
112843	R4	4500'	189		Start S+L Run in pollution layer. Tr. Ca to left now
1129					Non-uniform aerosol - interesting!
1130					clear slot to left → 2 aerosol layers?
1136	R4	4500'	190		seems to be just above & just below clouds (small cu) CN ~ 7500/cc } good!! 453010 ~ 6000/cc } clear above & below now
					Plat ~ 2 ppb (v. bright!)
113841	R4	4500'		44.6 12.7	End Run (S+L)
114000	P5 ↓	4500' ↓	077	44.6 12.8	Start profile descent to next level in pollution layer
		4000'			below most of aerosol? can see base of pollution, but CN still high
114236	P5/25	3500'	015	44.7 12.8	End profile / Start S+L
1143					Counts dropping off on all instruments. CO down to

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
114935	R5	3500'		45.2 12.9	End Run S+L. Filters out.
115218	P6↓	3500'↓	200	45.2 12.8	Start profile descent 500 ft/min
115542	P6→	1500'→	199	45.0 12.7	Interrupt profile (to turn) Skies clear above + below
115738	P6↓	1500'	023	45.0 12.8	winds 5 ^{ms} 130 deg. Sea state ~2
115952	P6.	100'	012	45.1 12.9	end profile descent. Wb of CN ~ 10 ⁴ /cc.
120356	R6	100'	201	45.1 12.7	S+L Run low level into Sun. * (New filter in) CN ~ 11,000 /cc. APAS → different aerosol to PL EPL
					Structure in CN. Evidence to right → local sources possible.
120836	R6 →	~200'			Rise = height.
120917	R6 →	100'	203	45.8 12.5	Re-start run (!) (Qazim ~ 204) EN ~ 15,000 /cc.
121256	R6		204	45.7 12.4	End Run (at dangerous) Heading back to ocean tower
122407	011)	400'		45.2 12.4	Start set of orbits Ocean = 9.14 ⁰ (~30 miles)
122540	012)	400'		45.2 12.4	over ocean tower.
122712	013)	400'		45.3 12.4	
122842	014)	400'		45.3 12.4	
123016	014 →	400'		45.3 12.4	End set of orbits. 60° left wing down. SWS change over.
124042	015)	400'		45.3 12.4	Start set of orbits. over Tower left wing down.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date **28/08/04**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124212	016↑	400'			Next orbit -
12434	017↑	400'			" " over tower.
12450	018↑	400'			Rivad orbit !! $Q_{sp} = 1.03$
124638	018 →	400' →			End orbits !!
124711	P27↑	400' →	161	45.2 12.4	Start profile ascent (4000 ft in air way) Climbing into pollution layer for fuel legs. 2 pollution layers visible to left of a/c. Some small Cn also in pollution tops.
125109	P27 →	500' →	151	45.0 12.6	End profile / start run stc in pollution. Cn ~ 7000 ft lower than MBL !!
125250	P27	500'	.	45.0 12.7	End Run !! Worth's shortest run?
125803					Official start of run - state !!
?	P28	500'			End Run. Over land, heading for Cn !!
→ Can use data from ~ 125400 z, after turn for home.					

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B044

Date: 28/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:27:50	Noise	Channel 2		8							Start P1 from 50'
08:32:25				8							FL020
08:33:30				5							FL030
08:34:55				8							FL040
08:35:30				8							FL050
08:36:30				2							FL060
08:37:20				2							FL070
08:38:00				2							FL080
08:39:00											FL090
08:39:50											FL100
08:40:50											FL110
08:41:40											FL120
08:42:35											FL130
08:43:25											FL140
08:44:16											FL150
08:48:21											FL160
08:49:20											FL170
08:50:13											FL180
08:51:25											FL190
08:52:25											FL200
08:53:26											FL210
08:54:25											FL220
08:55:15											FL230
08:56:20											FL240
08:57:52											End of Profile 1 @ FL250
09:00:11	New Tape										Start Orbits PCASP heaters ON
09:03:53											End of Orbits
09:09:47											Start of 3 rd Orbit
09:17:52											End of 6 th Orbit
09:39:07											Start Orbits
09:47:53											End of 10 th Orbit
09:52:16											Start Run 1.1 @ FL250

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:53:00	2										
09:55:00	3										
09:57:00	5										
09:59:00	5										End of Run 1.1
10:03:57											Start of Run 1.2 @ FL250
10:04:00	2										
10:06:00											
10:08:55											End of Run 1.2
10:15:39											Start of Run 1.3 @ FL250
10:16:00	4										
10:18:00	3										
10:20:00	2										
10:22:00	2										
10:24:00	2										
10:25:12											End of Run 1.3
10:31:27											Start Run 1.4 @ FL250
10:32:00	2										
10:34:00	4										
10:36:00	2										
10:36:39											End of Run 1.4
10:38:23	2										Start Profile 2 from FL250
10:39:20	2										FL240
10:40:23	7										FL230
10:41:10	7										FL220
10:42:20	4										FL210
10:43:10	6										FL200
10:45:10	2										FL190
10:46:05	5										FL180
10:46:40	5										FL170
10:47:20	5										FL160
10:50:10	15										FL140
10:51:10	13										FL130

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:52:00	20			1							FL120
10:52:40	13			1							FL110
10:55:03	25			1							FL100
10:56:13	80			1							FL090
10:57:20	80			1							End of Profile 2 @ FL080
11:00:01											Start Run 2.1 @ FL080
11:01:00	30			1							
11:03:00	15			1							
11:05:00	25			1							
11:07:00	35			1							
11:09:00	35			1							
11:10:01											End of Run 2.1
11:12:04											Start Profile 3 from FL080
11:13:18	130			8							FL070
11:14:25	180			8							FL060
11:15:19											End of P 3 and start Run 3 @ FL055
11:16:00											
11:18:00	360			8							
11:20:00	330			8							
11:22:00	320			10							
11:24:00	300			8							
11:25:12	300			10							End of Run 3 @ FL055
11:27:21											Start Profile 4 from FL055
11:28:55											End P 4 and start Run 4 @ FL045
11:29:00											
11:31:00	145			10							
11:33:00	300			10							
11:35:00	300			10							
11:37:00	200			10							
11:38:44	215			10							End of Run 4
11:41:01											Start Profile 5 from FL045
11:42:39											End of P 5 and start Run 5 @ 3500'

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:43:00	260			8							
11:45:00	290			5							
11:47:00	60			3							
11:49:30											End of Run 5
11:52:19											Start Profile 6 from 3500'
11:53:07	50			2							3000'
11:54:34	70			2							2000'
11:58:26	80			2							1000'
11:59:13	100			5							500'
11:59:53	90			5							End of Profile 6 @ 50'
12:03:56											Start Run 6 @ 100'
12:04:00	60			5							
12:06:00	100			5							
12:08:00	150			5							
12:10:00	250			10							
12:12:00	500		Overheat	10							
12:12:51											End of Run 6
12:15:50											PCASP Heaters OFF
12:24:06											Start Orbit 11 @ 400'
12:30:17											End of Orbit
12:40:42											Start Orbits (12) @ 400'
12:46:40											End of Orbits
12:47:11											Start Profile 7 from 400'
12:48:08	90			5							FL010
12:49:00	70			5							FL020
12:49:56	100			5							FL030
12:50:57	220			5							FL040
12:51:50											End of P7 and start Run 7 @FL050
12:53:50											End of Run 7

SEADAS tape 1 offset = +10, Tape 2 offset = +20

PCASP channels 1,2, and 3 noisy. Conc figures for other channels only. FFSSP is switched off after overheat

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	28/8/04	Flight	B044
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRICK	
Departure	28081610 Z		Arrival	281315 Z	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0 27581	SWS NIR -... VIS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0sec	at time	071200 Z
Freezer temp	-5°C @ 081900 Z			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B044	Date	28/8/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	1	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

074000Z									Dark Current - PRE TAKE OFF.
081259			90°A		AUTO				DATA Record - Start
081240									VIDEO Record - Start
081610									TAKE OFF
081800			0°						
082750	P1	500ft → 250000	0°						START P1
083000									Software change: Min int set to 10ms
			0°	75	2000				1000, 1500 & 2000ms added to ramp.
									Sample period set to 4s
084130									2000ms int period removed. Sample set to 2s
* 084135									Accidental dark current. no shutter. Ignore.
084330					AUTO				Data restart
084424		150	0°						interrupt P1
085630			6°F						in prep for orbits
085740		FL250							END P1
090011	ORBIT 1	FL250	6°F	10ms	10ms				45° Left wing down
090202	2								END 1: Start 2
090353	2								END 2. Unable to maintain height/speed. descending to try again.
090948	ORBIT 3	FL230	6°F	10ms	10ms				45° Left wing down. 0.2 sec sample period
091147	4	230	6°F	10ms	10ms				end 3: Start 4
091353	5	230	6°F	10ms	10ms				end 4: Start 5
091553	6	230	6°F	10ms	10ms				end 5: Start 6
* 091752	6								END. INSERT FILTERS
092410			6°F	15ms	30ms				NIR ND 3. Vis ND 3 0.2 Secs Sample
093907	orbit 7	230	6°F	15ms	30ms				40° Left wing down. (approx bank angle)
094118	8	230	6°F	15ms	30ms				end 7: Start 8
094328	9	230	6°F	15ms	50ms				end 8: Start 9
0944537	10	230	6°F	15ms	50ms				End 9: Start 10.
094753	10								end orbit 10.
095216	R1.1	250	46°F	15ms	30ms				into sun run. Zenith 40.7°. Pitch 6°.
100217	R1.1				AUTO				END RUN
100357	R1.2	250	0°	1500	1500				Across sun. 2 second sample period.
100855	R1.2	250							End
101539	R1.3	250	31°A	15ms	30ms				Down Sun run. 0.2 sec sample.
102512	R1.3				AUTO				END
103127	R1.4	250	180°	1500ms	1500ms				Across sun. 2 sec sample period.
103629	R1.4	250	180		AUTO				end run
103823	P2	250		1500	1500				start P2 FL250 → 080
104739	P2	159	180°						interrupt

Filters Fitted

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 044	Date	28/08/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

104822	P2	159	180°	1500	1500	Auto	Recommencing P2		
105305	P2	106	180°	1500	1500		Interrupt P2		
105437	P2		180°	1500	1500		Recommencing P2		
105720	P2	080					end		
110001	R2.1	080	43°F	15ns	30ns		INTO sun run.		
111001	R2.2	080					end of run		
111204	R3 P3	055					Start P3 F080 → 055		
111519	P3	055		15ns	30ns		end P3		
	R3		32°A				Start R3 0.2 secs sample period.		
111730							Video stop		
111745							Video start (new tape)		
112512	R3						end R3		
112721	P4	055 → 045							
112855	P4						end P4		
	R4	045	42°F	15	30		start R4 - into sun run		
113844	R4	045	42°F				end of run		
114101	P4.5	045 → 035	30°A	15	30		Profile 45 from F045 → F035		
114236	P4.5						end profile		
114236	R5	035	31°A	15	30		Start run 5 into sun		
114928	R5	035	31°A	15	30		end of run. Croatia looms.		
115219	P5	035 → 100ft							
115400			0°	1500	1500	Auto	2 second sample selected.		
115544	P6	1500ft					interrupt P6 @ 1500ft		
115740	P6						Recommencing P6		
115830			31°A	15	30		0.2 secs sample period.		
115953	P6	100ft					end P6		
120142			0°	15	30				
120356	R6	100ft	44°F	15	30		Start of R6 @ 100ft		
120856	R6	100ft					interrupt		
120916	R6	100ft					Recommencing R6		
121251	R6						end of R6		
121420			0°	1500	1500	Auto			
122406	orbit 11	400ft	6°F	10ms	10ms		40° Left wing down		
122537	11-12	400ft	6°F	10ms	10ms		end 11: start 12		
122714	13	400ft	6°F	15ns	50ns		end 12 start 13		
122848	14	400ft	6°F	15ns	30ns		end 13. Start 14		
123017	14	400ft	6°F				and 14.		
123740							FILTERS OUT. ***		
124042	orbit 15	400ft	6°F	10ms	10ms		40° Left wing down. 0.2 secs sample.		
124214	16	400ft		10	10				
124343	17	400ft		10	10				
124512	18	400ft		10	10				

F. H. us
sitted

*

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B044	DATE: 28/07/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: N Adriatic, near Venice, N Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX – flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols near Venice	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	1920 psi / 133 bar	2370 psi / 162 bar	720 psi / 50 bar
POST FLIGHT	1820 psi / 127 bar	2320 psi / 161 bar	720 psi / 50 bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)
27/08/04 12:36:47			87.62	65.89	5773.50	-	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.											
28/08/04 07:01:49	Ground	-	87.68	67.38	5907.82	550.328	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: First cal of day. Air sample pipe closed. CO max values 560 levelling to 525											
07:06:38	Ground	-	86.32	68.22	5888.20	563.392	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: ASP closed. CO max values 525-518											
07:35:31	ground	-	83.96	69.60	5843.60	189.387	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: ASP closed. CO max values 512-516											
08:14:39	ground	taxiing	90.34	68.27	6167.55	202.395	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: ASP closed. Post power changeover/CO reboot.											
08:24:09	FL050	-	85.70	69.20	5930.31	124.113	68	-0.03	1.07	1.04	5.77
Flow Lamp: 33.95 Press Monocr 0.76 Press Cell: 7.15 Press Cal Gas 2.30 Lamp °C 50.00 Monocr °C 26.04 PMT °C 25.99											
Remarks: Air sample pipe now open.											
09:01:20	FL250	O1	-	-	-	-	59	0.02	0.30	0.23	9.89
Remarks: CO cal ran into start of Orbit 1 (which began as Averaging started)											
09:22:18	FL230		89.67	63.92	5731.37	72.045	55	-0.14	0.31	0.12	8.64
Flow Lamp: 33.95 Press Monocr 0.64 Press Cell: 7.15 Press Cal Gas 2.22 Lamp °C - Monocr °C - PMT °C -											
Remarks: CO max values: 539-543											
09:30:01	FL250		89.89	63.46	5704.68	83.180	61	-0.10	0.25	0.15	8.70
Remarks: CO max values: 532-524 (despite drop in altitude as profile began before end of cal)											
10:28:46	FL250	R1.3 >	92.22	60.33	5563.58	67.687	57	0.09	0.11	0.20	8.82
Flow Lamp: 33.91 Press Monocr 0.63 Press Cell: 7.15 Press Cal Gas 2.22 Lamp °C 50.00 Monocr °C 24.63 PMT °C 24.56											
Remarks: CO max values: 524-527											
11:00:54	FL080	> R2	93.12	60.87	5667.84	94.61	59	-0.01	0.27	0.26	5.45
Remarks: CO max values : 534-529. Cal ran into R2 by approx 50 seconds.											
11:19:23	FL055	R3	93.36	61.09	5703.29	128	-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: CO max values : 529-525											
11:28:55	FL045	R4					-	-	-	-	-
Remarks: cal abandoned after 10-15 seconds due to potential interest in CO data at this level											
12:00:	FL015	P6	?	?	?	?	63	0.02	0.84	0.86	5.09
Remarks: CO max values :527-533 started in data interrupt but finished in second part of P6 so not a very good calibration.											
12:04:19	FL001	> R6	94.31	60.07	5665.41	124.114	62	-0.09	0.85	0.75	4.96
Flow Lamp: 33.98 Press Monocr 0.79 Press Cell: 7.16 Press Cal Gas 2.34 Lamp °C 50.00 Monocr °C 24.55 PMT °C 24.48											
Remarks: CO max values: 525-527. Run called while still descending from 150' to 100' so cal not at constant level											
12:55:33	FL050	R7	90.77	61.13	5549.01	126.275	-	-	-	-	-
Flow Lamp: 33.98 Press Monocr 0.76 Press Cell: 7.15 Press Cal Gas 2.33 Lamp °C Monocr °C PMT °C											
Remarks: CO max values: 511-503											
::	FL										-
Flow Lamp: Press Monocr Press Cell: Press Cal Gas Lamp °C Monocr °C PMT °C											
Remarks: CO max values:											
::	FL										-
Flow Lamp: Press Monocr Press Cell: Press Cal Gas Lamp °C Monocr °C PMT °C											
Remarks:											
::	FL										-
Flow Lamp: Press Monocr Press Cell: Press Cal Gas Lamp °C Monocr °C PMT °C											
Remarks:											

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

 Flight No. **B...044**.....

 Date **28.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS			FFSSP		✓
Satcom C			PCASP		✓
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	✗	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	✗	
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope	✗	
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2	✗	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	✗	
G. Eastern			HVPS	✗	
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	✗		INC	✗	
TWC	✗		CCN / CNC	✗	
FWVS	✓		CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear			PSAP		
“ Red			Nephelometer		
“ Silicon	✗	✓	AMS		✓
“ JO1D		✗			
Lower Clear					
“ Red					
“ Silicon		✓			
“ JO1D		✗			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	✗				
MARSS	✗				
DEIMOS	✗				
ARIES	✗				
SWS / SHM		✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		✓			
ECGC	✗				
NOX		✓			
CO		✓	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	✗				
PAN		✓			
PERCA	✗				
WAS		✓			

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B044

Instruments

1. Corcon aft o/b pc display locked up. reset pc.
2. XRSm GPS - Nav degraded
3. PSAP - display numbers not corresponding with horace.
4. FFC - window needs cleaned, smudges all over centre of picture
5. AFSSP - had to sw. off in flight 121549, too noisy.
6. PCASP - noise as yesterday.

PSAP Lin cal.

- Nick P has Floods room keys! No one can get into room...
- Can we give Giorgio a flight?

Aircraft

- Intercom - all on training etc in cabin today to avoid conflict ~~between~~ pilots / scientists transmissions
At faster (Simon some vol. At Roberts v loud.
- Bank lock failed? Gyro.
Some problem as before, ADIs have failed to erect correctly

©FAAM2004

New plot, same times

Flight B044 09:32:48

Heading 324 deg Speed 360 knots Height 23.0kft Press 408mb

Lat 44.7N Long 12.9E Wind 15 ms-1/ 272 deg

Temp -21.77C Dewpoint -33.13C

From 08:44:58 to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	34385	secs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All
— INS ROLL	-1.07	deg (+ve stb)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
— INS PITCH	4.03	deg (+ve up)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

B044 28-Aug-04 06:59:41 000 (06:42:24) 45.65 12.2

Event mark

<input type="radio"/> 81.UPOS	4644	21028	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 82.UPI5	5401	21785	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 84.UPOZ	826	9018	<input type="radio"/>
<input type="radio"/> 85.UPIZ	1364	9556	<input type="radio"/>

N/A	N/A

81.UPP VIS CLR SIG
82.UPP VIS RED SIG
83.UPP I/R SIGNAL
84.UPP VIS CLR ZERO
85.UPP VIS RED ZERO

All at 13 bits